

Plant hosts of rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guenée)

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Twelve rice field weeds were compared to rice as hosts of rice caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (see table). Rice caseworm eggs from a greenhouse colony were placed in cages around potted vegetative-stage plants immersed in water. Developing larvae were forced to feed on one plant species in this no-choice trial. Results showed that the rice caseworm is highly polyphagous and could survive rice-free periods on alternative hosts. Low larval survival on rice was caused by the small volume of water used in each potted plant in the experiment. Despite this deficiency, the rice caseworm survived on 8 of 12 weed species tested. *Paspalum conjugatum* was equal to rice in survival and developmental time. *Echinochloa colona*, *E. glabrescens*, and *Cynodon dactylon* were poorer hosts than rice. Rice caseworm survived poorly on *Paspalum paspalodes* (= *distichum*), *Leptochloa chinensis*, *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*, and *Eleusine indica*. There was no survival on the sedges *Cyperus difformis*, *C. iria*, and *Fimbristylis miliacea* (= *littoralis*).

Eight grasses and four sedges compared with rice as suitable plant hosts to the rice caseworm.^a IRRI, 1980.

Plant	Survival from egg to pupa (%)	Development time from egg to pupa (no. days)	Eggs laid by first-generation moths reared on plant host (no./female)
Poaceae (Gramineae)			
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	52 a	17.2 a	171
<i>Paspalum conjugatum</i>	38 ab	20.0 a	177
<i>Echinochloa colona</i>	28 b	18.4 a	179
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i>	25 b	19.4 a	153
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i>	25 b	18.6 a	200
<i>Paspalum paspalodes</i>	7 c	19.5 a	194
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i>	5 c	20.0 a	163
<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i>	11 c	29.7 ab	72
<i>Eleusine indica</i>	8 c	23.8 ab	0
Cyperaceae			
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i>	1 c	35.0 b	—
<i>Cyperus difformis</i>	0 c	—	—
<i>Cyperus iria</i>	0 c	—	—
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i>	0 c	—	—

^aFive replications/plant species, 20 eggs/replication. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different (P = 0.05).